

A cooling approach for a fuel cell aircraft engine using finned surfaces

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Abstract

The FAME project looks for the multidisciplinary design optimization of a 2.5 MW fuel cell-powered aircraft engine. The concept of having a finned nacelle as a surface heat exchanger for fuel cell cooling is explored. Numerical RANS simulations are performed to quantify the amount of heat transferred by the fins, as well as their effect on the drag to assess their feasibility. Two axisymmetric nacelles are tested along with fins attached to them. The thinner nacelle showcased a better behaviour in the presence of fins. The effect of propeller-induced swirl on the fins was studied as well.

1. Introduction

The FAMEⁱ project looks towards the development of a 2.5 MW fuel cell-powered aircraft engine in order to advance aviation towards a net-zero carbon emissions during flight, following feasibility assessments such as the ones of Meissner et al¹ and Ramm et al.² The project involves the multidisciplinary design optimization of the different systems present on the engine, including the design of a cooling system for the fuel cell, allowing it to keep it at a proper operating temperature of approximately 110°C. While traditional approaches include the usage of internal heat exchangers that dump the waste heat of the fuel cell into a flow of air taken from the freestream, alternative cooling methods are explored, which could result in cooling options involving less drag and weight on the nacelle. An approach of using the external nacelle surface as a heat exchanger is explored. The concept of external cooling has already been applied in certain studies such as the one of Kellermann et al³ and Anibal et al.,⁴ although the challenge for the current design is to deal with a massive amount of heat produced by the fuel cell with a limited nacelle area. Having an efficiency close to 55%, the 2.5 MW fuel cell generates a waste heat of around 2.0 MW.

Figure 1: Nacelle geometry designed by DLR.

Numerical calculations on the proposed nacelle configuration supplied by DLR (figure 1) have given insight into the maximum amount of heat that can be transferred by the available nacelle surface, excluding the hub. Considering the conditions presented in table 1 for cruise at an altitude of 8230 m (27 000 ft), a maximum amount of $Q_T \approx 0.4$ MW can be transferred through the nacelle area of 30.6 m². This considers the surface to be heated to a wall temperature of $T_w = R_T T_\infty$, with the temperature ratio $R_T = 1.6$. This puts T_w close to the maximum temperature achieved by the fuel

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cell. Realistically speaking, just a portion of the nacelle surface is sought to be used for cooling purposes, implying the necessity of enhancing the heat transfer capabilities of such heated zones by increasing their wetted area through fin attachment.

Table 1: Reference parameters at cruise conditions

Property	Symbol	Units	Magnitude
Reference length	L_{ref}	m	5.79
Reference area	A_{ref}	m ²	55
Freestream speed	U_{∞}	m/s	168.9
Angle of attack	AOA	°C	0
Static pressure	P_{∞}	Pa	34 761
Freestream temperature	T_{∞}	K (°C)	234.7 (-38.5)
Total temperature	T_0	K (°C)	248.9 (-24.8)
Surface temperature	T_w	K (°C)	375.5 (102.3)
Propeller Thrust	F_T	N	8095
Propeller Diameter	D_{prop}	m	3.97
Angular speed	ω_{prop}	RPM	850
Reynolds number	Re_L	-	$3.26 \cdot 10^7$
Mach number	Ma_{∞}	-	0.55
Prandtl number	Pr_{∞}	-	0.75
Temperature ratio	R_T	-	1.6

The current study focuses on performing RANS simulations using the software ANSYS FLUENT 23R2 of the flow over a nacelle on which heated fins are attached on some zones of its surface. These simulations are compared to unfinned cases as well to investigate the effect of the fins on the resulting integral parameters such as the total drag. To simplify the analysis, an axisymmetric reference nacelle was generated based on the DLR nacelle as shown in figure 2, designated as the reference axisymmetric approximation (A.A.). This allows for taking an angular portion of the entire geometry to perform the 3D simulation of only one fin, considering axisymmetric periodicity to account for swirling effects coming from the propeller. Additionally, based on this reference A.A., a new A.A. is presented as well, addressing some issues that the reference A.A. presents. The propeller is modeled as a minimum-induced-losses (MIL) propeller disk following the theory of Larrabee.⁵ It is noted that conjugate heat transfer is not taken into account in the present study; therefore considering the solid fin thermal resistance as zero.

Figure 2: DLR nacelle and its reference axisymmetric approximation (A.A.).

2. Integral parameters

The study centers on assessing the effect of the fins on the integral parameters of the nacelle. For this, the drag coefficient c_d is established in equation (2), being D the total drag force exerted on the nacelle and its hub streamwise.

$$c_d = \frac{D}{0.5 \rho_{\infty} U_{\infty}^2 A_{ref}} \quad (1)$$

The viscous drag coefficient $c_{d,v}$ is established from the viscous drag exerted on the nacelle surface D_v , from which the pressure drag coefficient $c_{d,p} = c_d - c_{d,v}$ can be calculated. The average Stanton number \overline{St} is then defined based on the total heat transfer Q_T from the nacelle or fins towards the air flow. The recovery temperature T_r is defined in equation (4), which takes into account effects of heating due to viscous work on a turbulent boundary layer (BL) as shown by Schlichting & Gersten.⁶

$$c_{d,v} = \frac{D_v}{0.5 \rho_\infty U_\infty^2 A_{ref}} \quad (2)$$

$$\overline{St} = \frac{Q_T}{\rho_\infty C_p U_\infty \Delta T A_{ref}} \quad (3)$$

$$T_r = T_\infty + Pr_t \frac{U_\infty^2}{2 C_p} \quad (4)$$

Since the mechanisms of surface heat transfer in a BL are correlated to the present wall shear stress, the thermo-hydraulic parameter γ is defined in equation 5 as the ratio between \overline{St} and $c_{d,v,heat}$, the latter being defined in equation (6), with $D_{v,heat}$ being the viscous drag exclusive only to the heated zone or heated fins. Thermo-hydraulic parameters have been used in studies such as the one of Webb & Eckert,⁷ Liao et al⁸ and Mhetras et al⁹ to quantify the ratio between the heat transfer and drag force or pressure loss in rough pipes, rib configurations and heat exchangers. In the current study, its formulation is constructed such that $\gamma = 1$ for a turbulent BL over an entirely heated flat plate at high Re_L . Therefore, γ allows for evaluating a configuration that delivers the most amount of heat for the existing amount of viscous drag in a specific zone.

$$\gamma = \frac{2 Pr_t}{R_T^{0.059}} \left(\frac{\overline{St}}{c_{d,v,heat}} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$c_{d,v,heat} = \frac{D_{v,heat}}{0.5 \rho_\infty U_\infty^2 A_{ref}} \quad (6)$$

Adding fins to the nacelle has the effect of incrementing both c_d and \overline{St} . To evaluate this impact, the variations Δc_d , $\Delta c_{d,v}$ and $\Delta \overline{St}$ are calculated according to equations (7), (8) and (9), respectively, being these the variations between a finned case and its respective unfinned nacelle case, heated on the same zone as where the fins are located.

$$\Delta c_d = (c_d)_{finned} - (c_d)_{no\ fin} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta c_{d,v} = (c_{d,v})_{finned} - (c_{d,v})_{no\ fin} \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta \overline{St} = (\overline{St})_{finned} - (\overline{St})_{no\ fin} \quad (9)$$

The thermo-hydraulic parameters of the fin β_{fin} and γ_{fin} are defined according to equations (10) and (11), respectively. γ_{fin} showcases the ratio between the gained heat transfer and the gained viscous drag. β_{fin} highlights the ratio between the gained heat transfer and gained total drag, which includes the added pressure drag due to the presence of the fins and separation generated at the end of the fins themselves. This implies that by careful design, $\beta_{fin} \rightarrow \gamma_{fin}$, although this is an aspect which will be studied in the future.

$$\beta_{fin} = \frac{2 Pr_t}{R_T^{0.059}} \left(\frac{\Delta \overline{St}}{\Delta c_d} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\gamma_{fin} = \frac{2 Pr_t}{R_T^{0.059}} \left(\frac{\Delta \overline{St}}{\Delta c_{d,v}} \right) \quad (11)$$

3. Nacelle & fin geometry

The base geometries for the simulations involve 2 nacelles as shown in figure 3, being these the previously presented nacelle reference A.A. and a thinner nacelle denoted as new A.A. The latter nacelle was designed to analyze the effect of its reduced thickness over c_d , which should become lower due to a reduction of $c_{d,p}$, as well as being less prone to flow separation.

The fin configuration to be tested and attached to the nacelles is presented in figure 4. These have a length $L_{fin} = 1$ m, thickness $t_{fin} = 0.002$ m, height $H_{fin} = 0.025$ m and base $Z_{fin} = 0.010$ m. The entire flow domain takes an

Figure 3: Geometrical comparison of original DLR nacelle, the reference A.A. and the new A.A.

Figure 4: Fin configuration (left) and front view of single fin (right).

axisymmetric slice equivalent to an angle θ_{dom} , big enough to be able to contain one fin and its corresponding spanwise base length to account for its height-to-base ratio of approximately 2.5 across the entire fin streamwise length.

Two streamwise zones for locating the fins were selected: a zone at $0.5 \text{ m} < x < 1.5 \text{ m}$, denoted as front zone, as well as a zone at $2.25 \text{ m} < x < 3.25 \text{ m}$, denoted as mid zone. Therefore, a total of 4 finned nacelle configurations are tested, being summarized in table 2, with their respective θ_{dom} , resulting in a specific number of fins covering the entire nacelle circumference. As an example of the resulting geometry, figure 5 presents the reference A.A. with fins located at the mid zone.

ID	Finned Zone	θ_{dom} [°]	Fins
-	-	-	-
Ref. A.A. - Front	$0.50 \text{ m} < x < 1.50 \text{ m}$	0.90	400
Ref. A.A. - Mid	$2.25 \text{ m} < x < 3.25 \text{ m}$	0.65	550
New A.A. - Front	$0.50 \text{ m} < x < 1.50 \text{ m}$	1.0	360
New A.A. - Mid	$2.25 \text{ m} < x < 3.25 \text{ m}$	1.2	300

Figure 5: Reference A.A. with fins located at the mid zone.

4. Numerical setup

The flow domain is constructed considering an embedded subdomain as shown in figure 6 (subfigure (b)), for which a fine 3D mesh was generated around the fin to take into account complex flow interactions. The rest of the flow domain presents a coarser mesh, although some refinement is present at the location of the propeller disk and the wake. All domains present an inflation layer next to the hub, nacelle and fin walls to account for the BL, for which maximum values of $y_0^+ \approx 0.7$ were achieved. The entire flow domain boundaries are located at a distance of $100 L_{ref}$. The resultant mesh presents around 4 million elements, being almost all elements allocated in the fin subdomain while almost 200 000 are distributed on the rest of the domain. The simulations present boundary conditions based on the parameters stated in table 1. The hub and the nacelle are treated with the no-slip condition, and the heat transfer is generated by setting a zone of the surface of the nacelle (or fins) at a wall temperature T_w . The rest of the surfaces are set as adiabatic.

Figure 6: Mesh for the flow domain. a) Mesh around the hub, with refinement around the location of the propeller disk. b) Mesh on top of the nacelle, with the fin presenting a higher mesh resolution around it (high-density mesh in the dark zone). c) Mesh around the back of the nacelle.

The numerical simulations were carried out using the software ANSYS FLUENT 23R2. These were compressible steady state RANS simulations, which take into account the heating due to viscous work. The simulations are considered to be fully turbulent and use the SST $k-\omega$ model of Menter.¹⁰ A constant turbulent Prandtl number of $Pr_t = 0.85$ was employed for the modeling of the turbulent thermal transport. For the modeling of the fluid properties, the specific heat capacity at constant pressure is $C_p = 1006 \text{ J}/(\text{kg} \cdot \text{K})$, while the dynamic viscosity μ and thermal conductivity λ are modeled via equations (12) and (13), respectively, being these power fits of data presented by Cengel & Cimbala.¹¹ The pressure-velocity is fully coupled in the solution. A second-order pressure scheme is used, as well as applying a second-order upwind scheme for the convective terms of the relevant transport equations. A least-squares cell-based scheme is used for the calculation of gradients.

$$\mu = \mu_\infty \left(\frac{T}{T_\infty} \right)^{0.736} \quad (12)$$

$$\lambda = \lambda_\infty \left(\frac{T}{T_\infty} \right)^{0.859} \quad (13)$$

A propeller disk was modeled following the formulations of Larrabee,⁵ which add axial and tangential sources in the disk region following the considerations for the design of a minimum-induced-losses (MIL) propeller. Therefore, the flow through the disk is slightly accelerated in the axial and tangential directions, creating a swirling motion. The propeller disk model only considers the lift component of the blades (no drag), and it presents the axial displacement velocity of the filaments of the formed vortex sheet as an input. This velocity is tweaked until obtaining the corresponding thrust F_T for a propeller with the specific diameter D_{prop} and angular velocity ω_{prop} . It is noted as well that the hub presents a tangential wall velocity since it is set to be spinning at ω_{prop} as well.

5. Results

5.1 Heat transfer on unfinned nacelles

Results for the numerical simulations of the unfinned nacelles are presented in table 3. Cases include the non-heated nacelles, as well as fully heating their entire surface. The heating effect can be observed by noting that the values of

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$c_{d,v}$ start to decay from the cases with no heating towards the fully heated ones, as noted in literature of BL heating by Schlichting & Gersten.⁶ Opposite to this, $c_{d,p}$ increases for the reference A.A. as heating increases due to a displacement on the already existing BL separation as seen in figure 7, while almost no change is seen in the new A.A. cases since BL separation is not present. Still, the results show a net decrease of c_d for both cases as more heat is introduced. It is noted as well that the maximum achievable heat transfer on the reference A.A. is of $Q_T = 0.387$, closer to the DLR nacelle which presents $Q_T \approx 0.4$. On the other hand, due to the reduced wetted area of the new A.A., a lower maximum $Q_T = 0.235$ is achieved. Nevertheless, a higher value of γ can be observed when contrasting the cases with mid heating to the ones with front heating, implying that a delayed heating of the BL brings more heat for less viscous drag, which is noted by Kays & Crawford.¹²

Table 3: Simulation results of unfinned nacelles

ID	c_d [10^{-3}]	$c_{d,p}$ [10^{-3}]	$c_{d,v}$ [10^{-3}]	\overline{St} [10^{-3}]	γ	Q_T [MW]
-					-	
Ref. A.A. - None	2.28	1.08	1.20	-	-	-
Ref. A.A. - Front	2.23	1.08	1.15	0.15	1.14	0.092
Ref. A.A. - Mid	2.25	1.08	1.15	0.17	1.16	0.106
Ref. A.A. - Fully heated	2.18	1.14	1.03	0.62	1.00	0.387
New A.A. - None	0.86	0.18	0.68	-	-	-
New A.A. - Front	0.83	0.19	0.64	0.12	1.15	0.074
New A.A. - Mid	0.84	0.18	0.66	0.10	1.37	0.061
New A.A. - Fully heated	0.78	0.19	0.58	0.38	1.08	0.235

Figure 7: Contours of non-dimensional velocity u/U_∞ of non-heated and fully heated reference A.A. and new A.A.

5.2 Heat transfer on finned nacelles

Results for the numerical simulation of the finned nacelles are presented in table 4. The increase of c_d , \overline{St} and Q_T in contrast to their corresponding heated unfinned case (table 3) can be easily noted. It can be seen as well that fins do not only bring into play an increase of $c_{d,v}$ but also of $c_{d,p}$, although the large discrepancy between γ_{fin} and β_{fin} suggests that the increase on pressure drag could be dealt with if careful design of the fins is considered. Also, γ values suggest that locating the fins towards the back of the nacelle increases their heat to viscous drag ratio, as noted previously in the unfinned cases, although risking BL separation.

Table 4: Simulation results of finned nacelles

ID	c_d [10^{-3}]	$c_{d,p}$ [10^{-3}]	$c_{d,v}$ [10^{-3}]	\overline{St} [10^{-3}]	γ	Q_T [MW]	β_{fin}	γ_{fin}
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ref. A.A. - Front	2.81	1.24	1.57	0.55	1.03	0.339	1.15	1.60
Ref. A.A. - Mid	3.31	1.62	1.70	0.66	1.06	0.409	0.76	1.49
New A.A. - Front	1.45	0.44	1.01	0.45	1.05	0.279	0.88	1.50
New A.A. - Mid	1.22	0.32	0.90	0.35	1.29	0.217	1.09	1.72

The increase of $c_{d,p}$ for the reference A.A. is dramatic as fins are moved backwards due to enhancement of the nacelle BL separation, as noted in figure 8. On the other hand, the new A.A. does not present such a strong effect since BL separation is non-existent on the nacelle, implying that its design should consider this aspect if fins are required to be implemented in the future.

Figure 8: Contours of non-dimensional velocity u/U_∞ of finned nacelles. Fins can be observed as shaded regions on the nacelle.

By plotting the c_p and c_f vs. x distributions over the finned nacelles, figure 9 is obtained. The separation behavior on the reference A.A. can be observed from c_f at $x \approx 5.5$ m on the unfinned case, being pushed forward to $x \approx 5.2$ m by the fins. The c_p distribution of the new A.A. is weakly altered only around the finned region, suggesting that the increase $c_{d,p}$ is happening at the fins, implying that a better fin design would be required to reduce this value, as previously noted.

A notable effect can be observed on the c_f distributions: wall shear stress is reduced after the fins, which is a consequence of local BL separation at their backs, as seen in figure 10, creating a region of low shear. This after-fin decrease of c_f counteracts the added $c_{d,v}$ of the fin surface, being this effect the reason of why values γ_{fin} appear well above unity in comparison to γ , which does not take into account the after-fin c_f reduction.

5.3 Effect of propeller swirl

Simulations were performed by removing the tangential source components of the propeller disk model to suppress swirl and compare these new results with the already obtained swirling cases. Both unfinned and finned nacelle geometries were taken, but only for the front zone arrangement. Table 5 summarizes the results. Although the overall c_d and $c_{d,p}$ values appear to be lower for the finned cases when compared to table 4, they are also lower for the unfinned cases in the same proportion when compared to table 3, being a $\Delta c_d \approx 0.58 \cdot 10^{-3}$ between the swirling and no-swirl reference A.A. cases, and a $\Delta c_d \approx 0.64 \cdot 10^{-3}$ between the swirling and no-swirl new A.A. cases. This results in almost

Figure 10: Contours of non-dimensional velocity u/U_∞ of the reference A.A. with fins at the mid zone. a) Flow around the front of the fins. b) Flow around the back of the fins. After-fin separation, which slowly recovers streamwise.

the same values of β_{fin} and γ_{fin} when compared to the cases with propeller swirl, implying that swirl does not have any exclusive effect over fins. It is observed that \bar{St} and Q_T also remain unaffected if swirl is removed.

Table 5: Simulation results of finned nacelles with no propeller swirl

ID	c_d [10^{-3}]	$c_{d,p}$ [10^{-3}]	$c_{d,v}$ [10^{-3}]	\bar{St} [10^{-3}]	γ	Q_T [MW]	β_{fin}	γ_{fin}
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ref. A.A. - Front (Unfinned)	1.96	0.81	1.15	0.15	1.14	0.092	-	-
Ref. A.A. - Front (Finned)	2.54	0.98	1.56	0.54	1.03	0.338	1.14	1.60
New A.A. - Front (Unfinned)	0.50	-0.14	0.64	0.12	1.16	0.074	-	-
New A.A. - Front (Finned)	1.16	0.16	1.00	0.45	1.05	0.278	0.82	1.50

6. Conclusions

Numerical simulations on 2 axisymmetric nacelle geometries were performed, on which fins were attached at certain zones streamwise. Comparison of the gain of heat and drag was done with their corresponding unfinned versions, where heating was applied on the same attachment zone.

Fins tend to enhance the heat transfer as expected, although their effects are different on bluff and slender nacelles: fins eventually increase the effect of an already present BL separation (reference A.A.), pushing it upstream and increasing the pressure drag dramatically. This effect becomes stronger if fins are pushed backwards streamwise. On the other hand, pressure distribution is weakly affected by the presence of fins on slender nacelles (new A.A.), although increase of pressure drag is exclusively due to separation on the back of the fins. The difference on the thermo-hydraulic parameters β_{fin} and γ_{fin} on the slender finned nacelle suggests the possibility of decreasing the gained pressure drag by properly designing more streamlined fins.

It is noted as well that the BL separation located after the fins drastically reduces the wall shear stress after them, countering their natural increase of viscous drag due to their extra wetted surface. This is a notion which has to be taken into advantage in their design, which, combined with a proper aerodynamic design, would allow to have a lesser effect on the total drag due to their implementation.

Finally, the effect of the swirl on the fins was analyzed, noting that it indeed has an overall effect on the drag characteristics of the nacelle, although no effect on the fins: the drag increase provided by the fins is still the same in cases with no swirl, while the heat transfer enhancement is unaffected.

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